

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

GAPs Indicator Proposal: Adopting Policy Effectiveness Framework into Return Governance

Authors:

**Fatma Yılmaz-Elmas¹, Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek¹, Rodrigo Bolaños Suárez¹,
Soner Barthoma²**

¹ Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies

² Uppsala University

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Abstract

This report presents an indicator proposal to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of return governance by systematically linking policy design, implementation practices, and observable outcomes. Building on the policy effectiveness framework developed by Czaika and de Haas (2013) and insights from GAPS' research addressing return policy frameworks (WP2), return infrastructure (WP3) and return cooperation (WP4), the proposal combines *instrumental* dimensions (such as legal clarity, institutional capacity, coordination, costs, and implementation performance) with *normative* dimensions (human rights, protection guarantees, and reintegration sustainability).

The indicator proposal is structured around three interconnected stages: policies on paper, policy implementation, and outcomes. For Stage 1 (policy on paper), it identifies dimensions and relevant indicators that capture the presence, clarity, and coherence of legal bases and safeguards; the configuration of institutional and administrative design (roles, coordination mechanisms, resources, stakeholder involvement, and data infrastructures); and the formal architecture of international cooperation, including intra-EU coherence, EU-level agreements, bilateral and informal arrangements, and alignment with non-migration policies.

Stage 2 (implementation) mirrors these dimensions to evaluate how far formal commitments translate into practice, focusing on implementation consistency, operational safeguards, monitoring and accountability, functioning coordination, use of financial and human resources, stakeholder participation in practice, and the real operation of cooperation and readmission mechanisms.

Stage 3 (outcomes) moves beyond simple return numbers to capture a differentiated set of policy effects. Direct policy effects are assessed through return figures (volume and efficiency), changes in the composition of returnees, and geographical destination patterns. External and relational outcomes focus on the quality and sustainability of cooperation with third countries and the role of power asymmetries and historical ties. Reintegration outcomes are captured through "reintegration capacity in origin countries", covering policy commitment, institutional and administrative capacity, service provision, labour-market absorption, and monitoring systems. Individual and social outcomes encompass migrants' livelihoods, living conditions, rights protection, (re)migration behaviour, exposure to chain deportation, community acceptance, social tensions, media framing, and local development effects. Finally, a separate dimension on substitutive effects addresses unintended consequences such as route shifts, burden shifting across control mechanisms, and the production of "non-removable" returnees, conceptualised as policy externalities.

The report also suggests a flexible scoring, scaling, and weighting proposal rather than a fixed composite index. For policy stages, indicators are generally scored on an ordinal scale and can be aggregated additively, multiplicatively, or through hybrid designs depending on whether components are treated as substitutable or necessary; for outcomes, mixed quantitative and qualitative evidence is normalised to a common scale, with explicit benchmarks (country-over-time, regional averages, or theoretical ideals). Moreover, there is need for transparency in methodological choices, the need to consider thresholds for core safeguards, and the importance of sensitivity analysis and data validity.

1. Introduction

Migration, especially return governance, is inherently complex, involving multiple actors and levels of governance. It is often influenced by conflicting national priorities, international commitments, and normative standpoints (Czaika & de Haas, 2013; Pasetti & Lebon-McGregor, 2023; Sahin-Mencütek et al., 2021). This complexity hinders the clear and comparable assessment of return policies' effectiveness. In this context, this report introduces an analytical framework, a set of indicators, and a system of weighting and scales to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of return governance by combining instrumental aspects (costs, implementation, procedural performance) with normative ones (human rights, protection, reintegration sustainability).

Assessing the effectiveness of migration policies within this governance context is not merely a technical task but a complex analytical and methodological challenge. A key difficulty is the absence of a consensus on what constitutes a “successful” or “effective” return. Different evaluations rely on varying criteria—ranging from return rates and human rights adherence to the sustainability of reintegration—leading to inconsistent assessments of success. *Instrumental* benchmarks that focus on physical removal contrast with *normative* benchmarks that emphasizes rights, protection and sustainable development leading to different and sometimes conflicting metrics of effectiveness (for discussions see also Lepsa-Rogoz et al. 2024; ECA 2021; Cassarino, 2004).

Different types of return - primarily forced, (assisted) voluntary, and spontaneous - further shape how effectiveness is defined and achieved, shifting the balance between instrumental goals (efficiency and speed) and normative goals (human rights and sustainability) (see Şahin-Mencütek, 2024). The resource-intensive (high financial cost) nature of forced returns (Saleh et al., 2026), both in terms of financial expense and human rights considerations (Warda & Al-Obaidi, 2026), emphasises the need to focus on outcomes when evaluating effectiveness. Scholars highlight that measures such as specialised independent monitoring systems for coerced returns, involvement of NGOs and civil society in the AVRR programs, and more genuine and longer-term reintegration support programmes can foster higher levels of trust and governance outcomes (Mielke et al 2025; Lepsa-Rogoz 2024; Sahin-Mencutek & Barthoma, 2026).

Limits of the existing data infrastructure, which struggles to capture outcomes across different governance models, further constrain the assessment of effectiveness (Yılmaz-Elmas & Schapendonk¹, *forthcoming*, see also GAPS WP3 country and synthesis reports²). Although the dominant policy benchmark in the EU is the return rate, that is, the percentage of return decisions that are actually enforced, its measurement suffers from methodological ambiguities, raising questions about its analytical value as an indicator for assessing policy (in)effectiveness (Stutz 2025). This ambiguity is further exacerbated by the multi-actor and transnational nature of return

¹ See Yılmaz-Elmas and Schapendonk (forthcoming, 2026) for a detailed analysis of return migration infrastructures (RMIs) and the role of datafication in shaping return governance. Drawing on a meta-analysis of publicly available datasets on return migration, the study demonstrates how uneven and fragmented data constitutes a methodological challenge for assessing policy effectiveness and includes a summary table of the datasets analyzed.

² All reports are available on GAPS project website www.returnmigration.eu

processes. Moreover, the empirical studies show that effectiveness depend on post-return and reintegration conditions , rather than enforcement alone (Koser & Kuschminder 2017; Wickramasekara 2019; Warda & Al-Obaidi, 2026; Uzomah et al., 2025; Jarosiewicz et al., 2025).

An important methodological challenge in measuring effectiveness is data selectivity. Despite repeated calls for “more data for better migration management”, most notably articulated in global governance frameworks such as the Global Compact (2018), current data structures tend to privilege formally recorded and administratively visible forms of return, while systematically overlooking coercive, informal, or hidden practices such as pushbacks, sudden removals, or returns occurring outside formal procedures (Papatzani et al. 2025). As such, effectiveness is often measured through indicators that reinforce dominant policy narratives rather than capturing a complete picture of lived realities.

Against this background, the GAPS project, as part of synthesising its findings, aimed to develop an analytical framework that demonstrates how to systematically evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of return governance. The aim is to clarify key dimensions of return governance and propose indicators that allow disentangling policy objectives, implementation practices, and observed outcomes across cases, thereby enabling some level of cross-country comparison without suggesting that findings can be universally generalised. It does not construct a composite index, but rather offers a framework that can serve as a necessary precursor to any index-building exercise on return governance, while also acknowledging its partial cover and the limitations of this exercise (see below).

Outline of the report

Following an introduction that positions the proposal within debates on return policy effectiveness and data limitations, the report in Section 2 establishes the conceptual and analytical framework. Subsequently, Section 3 describes the three stages (policy-on-paper, implementation, outcomes) along with their dimensions, indicators, and guiding questions. Section 4 offers guiding questions for each policy stage. Additionally, Section 4 presents options for scoring, scaling, and weighting when constructing indices or dimension-level scores, discusses limitations and external factors, and concludes with methodological guidance and references for future applications and potential index-building based on the proposed framework.

2. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

This Indicator Proposal is mainly based on the conceptual framework by Czaika and de Haas (2013), which aims to set clear benchmarks by “reconciling opposing views on policy effectiveness through distinguishing the different levels and dimensions at which migration policy outcomes are assessed” (p.488-489). Their approach suggests that differing conclusions about effectiveness often stem from studies referencing different levels of migration policy: public policy discourses (politicians' stated goals), policies-on-paper (actual laws and regulations), implemented policies (actual practices, affected by discretion, resources, interests, constraints), and migration policy outcomes. They contend that what is often called a “policy failure” is usually just a mismatch or misalignment between these levels.

To resolve opposing views and the complexity, Czaika and de Haas propose a framework that links these levels through three distinct “gaps” that can undermine policy effectiveness:

- (1) *discursive gap* (referring to the discrepancy between public discourses and the formal policy framework on paper),
- (2) *implementation gap* (referring to the disparity between policies-on-paper and their implementation in practice), and
- (3) *efficacy gap* (referring to the extent to which implemented laws and measures have the intended effect on migration flows - volume, timing, direction, and composition).

This conceptualization highlights that perceived policy failure generally stems not only from ineffective policies per se, but from gaps across policy levels and the influence of external migration determinants (e.g., labour market imbalances, social networks, non-migration policies). At the same time, Czaika and de Haas caution against treating “discursive gaps” as straightforward indicators of policy failure. Public policy discourse is often detached from formal policies, implementation resources, and actual policy effects, as it primarily functions as a symbolic instrument used by elected leaders to signal control and address public concerns. As such, discourse alone is an unreliable metric for assessing policy impact. Finally, although most quantitative research focuses on the written policies due to the difficulty of measuring implementation, this framework emphasizes that contextual knowledge and qualitative assessment are essential to evaluate whether formal policies are actually put into practice and how they reverberate across the different levels of governance.

A similar “gap” logic also underpins the ADMIGOV indicator framework (Pasetti & Lebon-McGregor 2023), which centres its indicators on the difference between “governance on paper” and “governance in practice”, thereby critiquing evaluations based solely on formal legislation. Both frameworks also recognize a discursive/normative gap. Czaika and de Haas define a “discursive gap” as the divergence between political rhetoric and actual laws; Pasetti & Lebon-McGregor (2023) identifies “normative gaps” where international standards of protection are not formally recognized in national law, though. Conceptually, both approaches also converge on a cyclical understanding of migration governance, despite using different terminologies for largely equivalent governance/policy stages. Pasetti & Lebon-McGregor (2023) uses four-stage governance process (*formulation, promulgation, implementation, and evaluation*),

corresponding closely to Czaika and de Haas's fourfold conceptual levels (*public policy discourses, policies on paper, implementation, and outcomes*).³

Despite structural overlaps, the two frameworks differ slightly in their understanding of effectiveness. Czaika and de Haas adopt an *instrumental perspective* focused on whether policies achieve their stated objectives (effectiveness is defined as producing a desired effect). ADMIGOV, by contrast, advances a *normative perspective* grounded in international standards of migration protection and human rights, complementing traditional instrumental component of efficiency and effectiveness.

The GAPS indicator proposal integrates instrumental and normative perspectives based on GAPS research. In their synthesis of GAPS three years of research, Sahin-Mencutek and Barthoma (forthcoming) identify five gaps in return governance. The first gap contrasts the rhetoric of “voluntary” or “assisted voluntary” return with coercive practices. The second gap is between policy expectations and actual return rates. The third gap involves the focus on “effective returns” in EU policies, which is undermined by fragmented practices. The fourth gap is the mismatch between political efforts to promote return for border control and the complex migration realities. The fifth gap is between the interests of return and receiving countries; return countries expect third countries to readmit their nationals, assuming that incentives will work, while third countries prioritise domestic concerns such as sovereignty, reintegration and development reconstruction.

From Policy Levels to Indicator Design

Drawing on conceptual foundations outlined above and on the empirical work of the GAPS project, we attempted to develop an analytical framework with indicator proposals to assess the effectiveness of return policies and practices. This framework largely adopts the policy levels identified by Czaika and de Haas as well as the empirical findings and conceptual frameworks adopted in the GAPS research, particularly its work packages addressing return policy and legislative frameworks (WP2), return implementation and infrastructures (WP3), return cooperation (WP5) and post-return experiences (WP8). In line with Czaika and de Haas' critique of discursive benchmarks and lack of adequate data in GAPS about this aspect, public policy discourse is not treated as a benchmark for evaluating effectiveness.

Effectiveness in this proposal is therefore assessed at the three interrelated stages: (1) policies-on-paper, (2) policy implementation, and (3) outcomes. By structuring the indicator framework around these **stages**, we seek to avoid reductionist assessments of effectiveness based solely on written policies or on return numbers. At each stage, we establish a set of indicators that integrate instrumental factors -such as the clarity and coherence of legal frameworks, procedural performance, costs, and organizational capacity- with normative elements from GAPS' own conceptual and empirical research. This combined normative and instrumental approach enables

³ There is also the policy cycle as outlined by Jann and Wegrich (2017) and by Schubert and Klein (2020): (1) Problem Formulation & Design – on how issues are identified, objectives are set, and return policies are designed; (2) Implementation – on the actual execution of return policies and programs; (3) Evaluation – on the standards and practices used to measure whether the design achieves its intended outcomes, respects rights, and is effective in practice; (4) Feedback & Reformulation – on how lessons learned from evaluation inform adjustments and improvements to future policies or its cancellation.

an assessment of return governance effectiveness throughout each stage, aligned with international protection and human rights standards. Essentially, this method helps identify not only whether return governance achieves its intended objectives (on paper) and results (return figures), but also where and why it may fall short, either in normative principles or practical implementation.

Within each stage, **dimensions** of effectiveness were identified by drawing on the key determinants discussed in the broader migration governance literature and in existing return indicator studies. These dimensions were then inductively refined on the basis of GAPs research findings in different work packages, particularly through the examination of empirical findings of Work Package 2 on legal and policy framework of seven EU countries, WP 3 on return infrastructures and practices in five EU and five non-EU countries, and WP5 on the meta-analysis of 58 return cooperation attempts between EU MS and third countries, including three in depth case studies of return diplomacy as well as post return experiences of migrants in four countries of origin. These work packages informed the selection of stages and dimensions, as well as the identification of recurrent challenges, such as fragmentation of competences, uneven monitoring, and the reliance on informal practices, that needed to be captured in any effectiveness assessment. In addition, insights from the GAPs concept note on Promising Return Practices (Bolaños Suárez et al., 2026), and from associated policy briefs⁴, helped specify what counts as better or worse performance within each dimension (for example, independent monitoring of forced returns, meaningful reintegration support, or transparent cooperation arrangements).

Together, these sources helped reflect the multidimensional and multilevel nature of return governance, encompassing core elements such as *protection principles, different stages of the return process, actors involved, different return categories, challenges across policy-cycle phases, and, to some extent, external factors.*

Limitations of the Proposal

The Indicator Proposal offers a structured analytical framework for assessing the effectiveness of return migration governance, but its scope is subject to several limitations:

1. **Framework-oriented, not index-based design:** The proposal puts forward a structured *indicator framework* rather than a fully operationalized composite index. It lays the conceptual and methodological groundwork on which such an index could be built and is intended as an analytical proto-type that can be adapted, combined into composite indices or used to refine indicators for specific policy stages or dimensions. Also, it proposes some basics about what could be the logic behind scaling and weighting as the follow up stage.
2. **Technical limitation:** Assessing policy effectiveness requires an explicit time frame for analysis and data collection. Without an explicit temporal scope (e.g., a ten-year assessment period), effectiveness assessments carry the risk of confusing short-term outputs with long-term outcomes, or the difficulty in interpretation and comparison.

⁴ See <https://www.returnmigration.eu/policy-briefs>.

3. **Piloting and validation process:** Given resource and time constraints inherent to the project, also consistent with the project's approved scope and deliverables, the proposal does not include a piloting or validation phase. However, the proposed indicators have undergone expert review by both the internal project partners and external reviewers. The framework also benefited from exchanges and consultation meetings with experts from a sister Horizon Europe FAIR project.
4. **Expert-based analysis:** Data collection, especially the indicators designed for implementation stages, requires expert-based analysis. To mitigate this limitation, future applications of the framework could combine systematic stakeholder consultation and administrative and qualitative data sources, with a robust internal review process, thereby increasing consistency and comparability across cases.
5. **External factors:** Migration outcomes, including return, are strongly shaped by other factors, including non-migration policies and structural determinants such as labour market imbalances and migration networks. As noted by Czaika and de Haas (2013), these factors can mask the desired impact of policies, leading to an apparent ineffectiveness even if the policy had some effect. Accordingly, while the GAPs Indicator Proposal aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of return governance effectiveness, it remains open to the influence of external factors beyond direct policy control. For this reason, the assessment should be done with caution: limited observable effects should not automatically be interpreted as policy failure. One way to address this is to complement with a non-scored contextual layer that identifies key structural and non-policy determinants (e.g., economic and political situation in origin country) relevant to the assessment period.

3. Dimensions Across Policy Stages

To develop the indicators, we first identified three policy stages: 1. Policy-on-Paper (laws, regulations, measures), 2. Policy Implementation (practice), 3. Outcomes. Each stage is divided into three to five dimensions, which were subsequently unpacked into concrete main indicators. The identification of dimensions and indicators went through several iterations, including merging, deleting, and replacing items based on experts' judgments. In the next step, the framework was operationalised through a set of guiding questions to structure the assessment of return governance across stages, which likewise required further iterations to minimise overlap and keep the list manageable for potential assessors. We will explain these steps below.

Stage1: Policy-on-Paper

This stage evaluates the formal and regulatory design of return policies, as specified in legal, institutional, and strategic documents. The focus is on the presence of clear legal mandates, procedural safeguards, administrative arrangements, coordination mechanisms, accountability provisions incorporated in the legal and policy framework, as well as on the extent to which international cooperation is formally structured. The analysis at this stage does not presume their implementation in practice. A normative perspective regarding safeguards by return types and return stages, access to legal remedies and appeals, and differentiation for vulnerable groups is embedded across dimensions.

Stage1: Policy-on-Paper (laws, regulations, measures)	
<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Main Indicators</i>
Legal Basis, Safeguards, and Accountability Provisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence and Clarity of Legal Framework about Return • Procedural Safeguards and Rights Guarantees • Independent Monitoring and Reporting
Institutional & Administrative Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity of Roles, Mandates and Institutional Configuration • Domestic Coordination Mechanisms • Financial and Resource Capacity • Stakeholder Involvement • Digital Infrastructure and Data Management
International Cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intra-EU Policy Coherence between National and EU Frameworks • Formal EU-Level Agreements & Support Instruments • Bilateral and (In)formal Arrangements • Alignment with Non-Migration Policies

Stage2: Policy Implementation

This stage evaluates how return policies are operationalized in practice. The effectiveness is assessed by mirroring the dimensions formulated during the policy-on-paper stage, shifting the analytical focus from the existence of a framework to legal and procedural practices, operational effectiveness, and the functioning of institutions, procedures, monitoring, and cooperation mechanisms. Evaluating implementation, therefore, requires contextual and qualitative research through field observation, interviews, and administrative data analysis, rather than reliance on policy documents alone.

Stage2: Policy Implementation (Practice)	
<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Main Indicators</i>
Legal Basis, Safeguards, and Accountability Provisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation Consistency with Legal Frameworks • Upholding Procedural Safeguards and Rights during Return Processes • Operational Monitoring and Accountability Practices
Institutional & Administrative Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity of Roles and Institutional Coordination in Practice • Operational Coordination Mechanisms • Capacity: Financial and Resource Management • Stakeholder Involvement in Practice • Operational Data Management
International Cooperation in Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Coherence with EU Return Frameworks: <i>Participation in Joint Return Operations and Cooperation Challenges</i> • Implementation of Formal EU Cooperation Frameworks and Funding Instruments • Functioning of Readmission Mechanisms • Policy Coherence and Alignment

Stage3: Outcomes

At the outcome stage, effectiveness is assessed through a differentiated set of dimensions that capture both the direct policy effects (volume of returns, composition of returnees, geography of returns) and the broader consequences of return governance. Moving beyond simple success metrics tied only to return figures, the framework advances considerations about return governance effectiveness and shifts the focus towards the sustainability of the return, emphasising migrants' post-arrival trajectories. The outcome dimensions are therefore designed to encompass not only quantitative indicators, but also qualitative effects, including reintegration trajectories, and wider societal or behavioural impacts, and unintended or substitutive effects. In doing so, this assessment stage incorporates dimensions such as return cooperation and reintegration capacity, to capture the impact of empirically essential factors, *albeit limited*, beyond immigration policy alone when assessing migration outcomes.

Stage3: Outcomes

<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Indicators</i>
Direct Policy Effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Return Figures (Volume & Efficiency)• Change in Composition (Profile of Returnees)• Geographical Direction/ Destination Patterns
External / Relational Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Return Cooperation with Third Countries
Reintegration Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reintegration Capacity in Origin Country
Individual and Social Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Migrants' Well-Being / Sustainable Reintegration• Community & Social Impact
Substitutive Effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Substitution and Unintended Effects

4. Guiding Questions Across Policy Stages

Building on the analytical dimensions outlined above, this section operationalizes the framework through a set of guiding questions that structure the assessment of return governance across stages.

Stages 1&2: Policy-on-Paper & Implementation

The framework below merges policy-on-paper (Stage 1) and implementation (Stage 2) into a single table to foreground the relationship between law and practice in return governance. This reflects the analytical premise that legal and policy frameworks are primary benchmarks against which implementation practices are assessed, and that legal design and implementation should be analysed as interconnected, rather than strictly sequential domains.

Operationalised across three main dimensions (as configured in the above section), a set of guiding questions is organised along the mirrored policy stages and serves as interpretive benchmarks rather than discrete, self-standing indicators. For each dimension, the questions probe how return-related regulations, institutional and administrative arrangements, and monitoring mechanisms are formulated in law and policy, and how they are implemented in practice, enabling a systematic evaluation of coherence and divergences between legal design and implementation. While internal legal clarity and coherence form the main reference points, EU and international legal standards already function as implicit normative references. Accordingly, the guiding evaluation questions at the implementation stage are analytically mirrored against the relevant legal and policy criteria identified in Stage 1, but are not limited to them.

1st Dimension - Legal Basis, Safeguards, and Accountability Provisions

The first dimension assesses whether return governance is rooted in a clear and consistent legal framework and whether the safeguards and accountability mechanisms embedded in law are effectively implemented in practice. It considers not only the formal presence of legal and procedural guarantees but also the extent to which these guarantees influence implementation, restrict administrative actions, and uphold compliance with fundamental rights and EU obligations.

We narrowed it down to three core indicators detailed below, mainly structured around (1) the presence and clarity of a legal framework, (2) safeguards and rights, and (3) monitoring and reporting. Taken together, these indicators enable a structured assessment of whether return governance functions within a legally sound, normatively coherent, respectful of rights, and accountable framework, bridging the gap between policy commitments and implementation realities.

Indicators are operationalised through a set of stage-specific guiding evaluation questions applied to distinct thematic foci of return governance.

Indicator 1: Presence and Clarity of Legal Framework - Implementation Consistency

This indicator assesses whether return-related rules are clearly defined in law or policy formulation, internally coherent, aligned with EU and/or international standards, and applied consistently by competent authorities in practice. Policy-on-paper are largely taken as benchmarks to assess the implementation, mainly because the formal legal design determines the operational structure and constraints of the policy, which influences ultimate effectiveness.

Specifically, it examines the clarity, consistency, and legal basis of key definitions and regulatory choices that determine when return is initiated, how it is carried out, and which safeguards apply. So, the thematic focus includes legal definitions (e.g., return, removal, voluntary return, irregular stay), AVR schemes, alternatives to return, the legal construction of irregularity, and the regulation of pre-removal detention. Ambiguity and fragmentation in these areas often lead to inconsistent implementation, uneven safeguards, and divergent practices across authorities.⁵

Indicator 2: Procedural Safeguards and Rights Guarantees – Upholding Safeguards in Implementation

For Indicator 2, the evaluation focuses both on whether procedural safeguards and rights guarantees are formally recognized, and also on whether they are effectively accessible and upheld throughout the return process. The formal design must include robust procedural safeguards, particularly concerning effective access to information and legal aid, and the implementation of guarantees related to the principle of non-refoulement, as well as return procedures respectful that respect human rights, with specific attention to detention conditions and the treatment of vulnerable groups.⁶

Although closely linked to the differentiation between voluntary and forced return in the previous indicator, since coercion can occur despite formal legal distinctions, voluntariness is treated here as a procedural safeguard rather than a definitional feature.

Indicator 3: Independent Monitoring and Reporting - Operational Monitoring and Accountability Practices

The thematic focus under Indicator 3 capture the effectiveness of accountability mechanisms through independent and external monitoring, as well as the existence of structured reporting and follow-up processes that can transform oversight findings and feedback into corrective action.

⁵ D2.1 GAPS comparative report, See <https://zenodo.org/records/11222075>.

⁶ D2.1 GAPS comparative report, See <https://zenodo.org/records/11222075>.

STAGES	POLICY -ON-PAPER	IMPLEMENTATION
Dimension 1	Legal Basis, Safeguards, and Accountability Provisions	
Indicator 1:	Presence and Clarity of Legal Framework	Implementation Consistency with Legal Frameworks
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Legal definitions	Are definitions of "return", "removal", "deportation" and "voluntary/forced return" clearly defined and consistent across legal instruments?	To what extent are these legal distinctions reflected and upheld in implementation practices?
		Is the distinction between voluntary and forced return reflected in practice (e.g., in documentation, statistics, and return counselling)?
AVR	Is there a formal legal or policy basis for assisted voluntary return programmes at national and/or municipal levels?	Are assisted return programmes actively implemented and accessible to eligible migrants in practice?
Alternatives to return	Are there any specific mechanisms providing legal status for "alternative to return", including regularization pathways, temporary residency/tolerated status, and humanitarian visas?	Are mechanisms for "alternatives to return" effectively implemented, and do eligible migrants actually receive these statuses or permits in practice?
	Are legal rights attached to alternative statuses clearly defined?	Do persons granted "alternatives to return" actually enjoy the legal rights attached to those statuses (e.g., access to healthcare, education, or work authorization)?
Irregularity	To what extent do national legal frameworks clearly and consistently define the legal grounds that place migrants in an irregular situation, across migration, asylum, border control, and employment legislation?	Do implementing authorities apply the legal grounds for irregular status consistently across cases, or do ambiguities and overlaps in the legal framework lead to divergent interpretations in practice?
	Are alternatives to detention formally provided for in law?	Are alternatives to detention used in practice as provided by law?

Pre-removal detention	Are legal maximum detention periods clearly defined in law?	How consistently do authorities apply the legal maximum detention period in practice?
	Do legal provisions restrict detention duration in line with international norms and standards?	If detention occurs (including de facto detention), does its duration comply with international norms and standards in practice?
	Are procedural safeguards and oversight mechanisms over detention established in law?	Are there monitoring mechanisms or independent bodies that verify that detention practices comply with detention safeguards (e.g., judicial oversight and review)?
	Are vulnerable persons explicitly protected from detention or subject to stricter safeguards in law?	Have any cases been reported where prolonged or unlawful detention of vulnerable persons was identified?
Indicator 2:	<i>Procedural Safeguards and Rights Guarantees</i>	Upholding Procedural Safeguards and Rights during Return Processes
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Availability & Accessibility	To what extent are general procedural safeguards clearly codified in national legislation and policy frameworks governing return procedures?	To what extent are the codified procedural safeguards effectively applied and upheld throughout return procedures in practice?
Access to information	Does the legal framework require that returnees are informed of their rights, remedies, and return options in a language they understand?	Are returnees in practice informed in a language they understand about their rights, return procedures, legal remedies and return options (including through interpretation or translated materials)?
Voluntariness	Are safeguards ensuring the voluntariness of return and informed consent clearly regulated in law?	Are there incidences of coercive practices (e.g., detention threats, status withdrawal, manipulation of consent) in the implementation of “voluntary” return?
Vulnerability assessment	Are there any specific legal provisions or arrangements concerning the return of vulnerable individuals, such as unaccompanied minors, pregnant women, persons with disabilities, and others?	Are individual vulnerability assessments systematically conducted before the enforcement of return?
		In practice, are vulnerable persons (e.g., unaccompanied minors, pregnant women, elderly, or persons with

Non-refoulement		disabilities referred to appropriate support services (health, psychosocial, housing)?
	Is the principle of non-refoulement directly enshrined in the constitution or national laws?	To what extent do return authorities assess and act upon protection risks in practice to prevent refoulement?
	Are safeguards against indirect refoulement explicitly codified in laws or policies governing externalisation practices and safe third-country designations?	Are there practices of indirect refoulement through externalisation or safe third-country concepts?
Deportation / removal orders	Are there specific legal safeguards against deportation or removal orders (right to appeal, suspensive effect, judicial review)?	Are appeals against return or deportation orders effectively processed, and do they have any suspensive effect (i.e., stopping removal until a final decision)?
		Despite the right to appeal, are deportation procedures carried out before the appeal decisions become final?
Arbitrary detention & humane treatment	Does the legal text prohibit arbitrary detention and ensure humane treatment during removal?	Are there instances of detention or removal occurring outside the legal framework (any practices of informal or de facto detention, or procedural shortcuts in detention and removal processes)?
	In case of detention, is there guaranteed access to legal counselling, interpretation, and contact with family/representatives?	Do detained returnees in practice have effective access to legal counselling, interpretation, and contact with family or representatives?
Indicator 3:	<i>Independent Monitoring and Reporting</i>	Operational Monitoring and Accountability Practices
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Independent monitoring	Does the legal framework include provisions mandating independent monitoring of return operations and detention (as required under Article 8(6) of the EU Return Directive)?	Does the authority mandated to monitor removals operate independently and effectively in practice?
	Does the envisaged monitoring cover all phases of a return operation, from pre-departure to arrival?	To what extent do independent monitoring bodies have access to all phases of the return process, including apprehension, pre-departure detention, and handover?

	Does the legal or policy framework envisage the involvement of monitoring bodies in both forced return operations and voluntary return programmes (AVR/AVRR)?	Are monitoring bodies in practice involved in voluntary return programmes (AVR/AVRR), or is monitoring limited to forced return operations?
	Is there an independent authority legally mandated to monitor removals?	How regularly are return operations monitored (e.g., every operation, random sampling, or spot checks)?
	Does the legal framework mandate independent monitoring of detention facilities?	Are there any reported cases of ill-treatment, coercion, or violations of fundamental rights during detention or return operations?
	Are alternative measures monitored to ensure their proportionality and compliance with human rights?	To what extent are alternative measures monitored in practice to ensure proportionality and compliance with human rights?
External monitoring	Are international organizations (e.g., IOM, Ombudsman institutions, NPMs) formally mandated to engage in monitoring or complaint-handling mechanisms?	Do international organizations (e.g. UNHCR) actually participate in monitoring or complaint-handling activities in practice?
	Are civil society organizations granted legal access to return-related sites (e.g., detention centres, transit zones) for monitoring purposes?	Can civil society organizations actually access detention centres, transit zones, or return operation areas in practice?
Reporting & follow up	Are there provisions requiring the competent authority to review monitoring findings and implement corrective measures?	Does independent monitoring result in demonstrable changes in practice? Do the findings in the monitoring reports lead to corrective measures, policy updates, or operational improvements?
	Is there a legal requirement to publish or disseminate monitoring reports to ensure external scrutiny?	Are monitoring findings made public or communicated to stakeholders to increase transparency?

2nd Dimension - Institutional & Administrative Design: Capacity, Resources, Coordination and Procedures

The success of the return policy, particularly evaluated through institutional and administrative design, can be gauged by several key indicators related to clarity, capacity, coordination efficiency, and accountability within the legal and operational frameworks. Institutional design pertains to the overarching structure, focusing on policy-making regarding returns, while administrative design concentrates on daily management and specific internal processes and operations. We grouped the indicators for evaluating institutional and administrative into five core indicators.

Indicator 1: Clarity of Roles, Mandates and Institutional Configuration - Implementation Consistency

The presence and effectiveness of special national institutional bodies dedicated to addressing return migration are the first indicators of a structured design. Evaluation should assess the consistency and certainty provided by the legal framework. Accordingly, Stage 2 Implementation questions evaluate whether these formally designated roles are effectively exercised in practice.

Indicator 2: Domestic Coordination Mechanisms – Operational Consistency

This indicator evaluates whether return governance is backed by effective domestic coordination mechanisms, both at the policy design stage and during daily implementation. By linking formal domestic coordination frameworks with their practical application, the indicator aims to measure the administrative capacity to turn coordination into the consistent and effective implementation of return procedures. The evaluation examines not only the formal inter-ministerial or inter-agency mechanisms and their operational arrangements but also the central-local coordination to assess the level of vertical coordination.

Indicator 3: Financial and Resource Capacity – Management Consistency

The scope and scale of the return policy mainly depend on existing financial and human resources. Its effectiveness is largely determined by the available financial resources in the budget to carry out the activities outlined in the policy agenda. Funding instruments are essential for providing specialised support or facilitating voluntary return, ensuring that policies align with humanitarian objectives. In this context, this indicator assesses whether the return policy is supported by a realistic, sustainable, and legally grounded financial and human resource framework.

Indicator 4: Stakeholder Involvement - Implementation Consistency

This indicator measures how much return governance is influenced by inclusive, structured engagement with relevant stakeholders, both during policy design and implementation. The assessment considers not only whether engagement mechanisms exist but also the quality of those interactions, including whether stakeholders' inputs are recognised or reflected in decision-making. Stakeholder roles related to independent monitoring and reporting are examined under Dimension 1 and are not reassessed here.

Indicator 5: Digital Infrastructure and Data Management - Operational Management

A critical challenge to the effectiveness of return governance is a robust administrative framework capable of systematic data collection, logistical use of data in workflows and case management.

GAPs comparative analysis and findings also highlight the pivotal role of systematic data collection in shaping policies that are both humane and aligned with human rights principles.⁷(GAPs WP2 Comparative Report, Promising Return Practices). In this regard, Indicator 5 evaluates whether return policies are supported by functional, standardized, and interoperable digital infrastructures that enable reliable data collection, case management, and institutional coordination.

⁷ See D2.1 GAPs comparative report, See <https://zenodo.org/records/11222075>. Concept note on Promising Practices of Return. <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/promising-return-practices>.

STAGES:		POLICY -ON-PAPER	IMPLEMENTATION
Dimension 2		Institutional & Administrative Design: Capacity, Resources, Coordination and Procedures	
Indicator 1:	<i>Clarity of Roles, Mandates and Institutional Configuration</i>	<i>Clarity of Roles and Institutional Coordination in Practice</i>	
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Designation of lead authority	To what extent is there a designated national authority, in law or policy, responsible for coordinating return migration policies, with a clearly defined mandate, decision-making authority, and coordination role?	In practice, does the designated national authority effectively coordinate and supervise return operations between the relevant ministries and agencies?	
AVRR assignment	Is AVRR management assigned to specific units and staff?	Are dedicated AVRR unit(s) and staff actively managing cases, ensuring consistent application of procedures and coordination with partners?	
Coherence		Have implementing actors reported disagreements regarding their areas of authority, duplication of tasks, or gaps in responsibility during the execution of return procedures?	
Indicator 2:	<i>Domestic Coordination Mechanisms</i>	<i>Operational Coordination Mechanisms</i>	
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Coordination structure	Is there an inter-ministerial or inter-agency coordination mechanism (e.g., steering committee, task force) that ensures policy coherence?	Are joint task forces, contact points, or liaison officers for returns in place and functioning?	
Coordination procedures		Are coordination platforms or digital tools (e.g., shared databases, case-management platforms, communication systems) used by the relevant institutions in implementation?	

Central-local coordination	Do laws or policy frameworks establish formal coordination mechanisms between central and local authorities for the implementation of return procedures?	Are coordination structures operational and effective both central and local levels in practice?
Indicator 3:	Financial and Resource Capacity	Financial and Resource Management
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Budget allocation & financial instruments	Does the migration policy include a clearly defined and proportionate budget for return and reintegration activities?	Have implementing actors or auditors reported whether the allocated financial resources were used effectively and proportionally in practice?
	Are financial or developmental incentives available to support or encourage voluntary return (e.g., cash assistance, credit, training)?	If any, are financial or developmental incentives (cash, credit, training, reintegration support) actually accessible to returnees in practice? Are there barriers or too much bureaucracy impeding easy access?
Human resources	Do laws, policies, or budgetary frameworks formally provide dedicated financial and human resources to support the lead authority's coordination role in return governance?	Does the lead authority, in practice, possess sufficient financial and human resources to carry out its coordination responsibilities effectively?
	Are specialised staff roles (e.g., caseworkers, legal officers, counsellors, detention staff, interpreters) formally assigned within the responsible institutions?	Is the current staffing level adequate to manage returns without delays, backlogs, or loss of efficiency?
		Is specialised staff (e.g., psychologists, interpreters, child-protection officers) genuinely available when required during return procedures?
Indicator 4:	Stakeholder Involvement	Stakeholder Involvement in Practice
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Stakeholder roles in policy formulation	To what extent are stakeholder roles in the negotiation and development of return policies formally established in law or official frameworks?	To what extent do civil society organisations, local governments, and social partners participate in negotiations or consultation processes in the formulation of return policies?

Stakeholder roles during the return process	To what extent do laws, policies, or formal cooperation frameworks facilitate the involvement of relevant stakeholders in the implementation of return policies?	To what extent are relevant stakeholders involved in the implementation of return policies in practice?
Quality of engagement		Can stakeholders access effective channels to give recommendations or raise concerns regarding return implementation?
		Is engagement ad hoc, consultative, or institutionalized?
		Are stakeholder inputs acknowledged or acted upon?
Indicator 5:	Digital Infrastructure and Data Management	Operational Data Management
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Existence and operation of data systems	To what extent do laws or policies require the establishment of institutional systems or databases for collecting and managing return-related data (voluntary, forced, AVRR, detention)?	To what extent are institutional systems or databases actively used to collect, record, and manage return-related data in practice?
Data standardization	Are data collection and sharing procedures standardised across agencies?	Do return databases accurately distinguish between return types (e.g., voluntary, forced, assisted), and reflect field-level classifications without mislabelling?
Data quality	Are there regulatory standards that define minimum requirements for return-related data?	Are there data gaps, delays, misclassifications, inconsistencies or accuracy issues?
The use of data in workflows	Are there legal provisions regulating how authorities should use data and digital tools in return procedures?	To what extent do authorities use digital tools and data systems to manage return cases, track information, and coordinate internally?
Data sharing & transparency	Are there legal or policy requirements for making statistical outputs and reports regularly available and accessible to relevant stakeholders to inform evidence-based policymaking?	To what extent are statistical outputs and reports regularly published and made accessible to relevant stakeholders to inform evidence-based policymaking and ensure transparency in return operations?

3rd Dimension- International Cooperation

International cooperation with third countries, especially countries of origin, at all stages of the return process is a prerequisite to achieving sustainable return (EU Directive 2008/115/EC), as physical removal inherently depends on the consent and assistance of the receiving state. Its effectiveness hinges on indicators that assess the degree of unification among member states (intra-EU policy coherence), the functioning of centralized EU support systems, the success of bilateral formal or informal engagement with third countries, recognition and enforcement of return decisions, data sharing, and alignment with non-migration policies (development, labour market, foreign, and economic policy). Accordingly, international cooperation is operationalized through four core indicators:

Indicator 1: Intra-EU Policy Coherence between National and EU Frameworks

Indicator 1 examines intra-EU policy coherence by assessing the alignment between national frameworks and EU rules, including the consistent application of common standards and mechanisms across member states. It focuses on coherence regarding key EU mechanisms, such as the Dublin system, mutual recognition of return decisions, data exchange, and participation in Joint Return Operations.

Indicator 2: Formal EU-Level Agreements & Support Instruments

The indicator examines the success of EU-wide external cooperation efforts with third countries, specifically focusing on EU Readmission Agreements (EURAs), the use of diplomatic leverage (incentives and conditionality), the execution of readmission procedures, and the role of stakeholder participation in both the formulation and implementation of these agreements.

Indicator 3: Bilateral and Informal Arrangements

This indicator assesses the role of bilateral and informal arrangements with third countries as practical tools for implementing return policies beyond formal EU-level agreements, including the existence and use of legally binding and more flexible arrangements, and the transparency of their negotiation and implementation. It evaluates not only the conclusion of agreements, but also whether implementation protocols are in place, whether joint readmission committees or working groups meet regularly to monitor compliance, and how operational coordination tools, such as travel documents and return liaison officers, are used to facilitate returns in practice.

Indicator 4: Alignment with Non-Migration Policies

This indicator assesses the extent to which return policies are coherently embedded within non-migration policy frameworks, particularly development, labour market, foreign, and economic policies. It also addresses diaspora engagement, assessing the recognition of diaspora actors as partners in voluntary return and reintegration processes and diaspora's involvement in planning of return/reintegration programs.

STAGES:		POLICY -ON-PAPER	IMPLEMENTATION
DIMENSION 3		International Cooperation	
Indicator 1:	<i>Intra-EU Policy Coherence between National and EU Frameworks (only for EU MSs)</i>		<i>Operational Coherence with EU Return Frameworks</i>
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions		Guiding Evaluation Questions
Dublin compliance	Does the national policy ensure compliance with the Dublin Regulation and prevent national practices that bypass EU return obligations, including non-refoulement?		Are return procedures being carried out in accordance with Dublin obligations, avoiding operational practices that circumvent responsibility sharing or undermine non-refoulement protections (e.g., fictitious no-entry zones, airport procedures)?
Mutual recognition of return decisions	Is there a clear legal and operational framework for "mutual recognition of return decisions" issued by other Member States?		Are return decisions from other Member States recognised and enforced as required?
Coherence regarding data sharing	Does the policy ensure interoperable and standardized return-related data exchange among Member States (through compliance with EIL statistical requirements, use of EU digital return systems (such as IRMA), and integration with SIS)?		Are EU digital return systems (e.g., IRMA, SIS) actively used in practice to enable standardized and interoperable exchange of return-related data among Member States?
Joint return operations	Does the policy establish legal and operational rules for participating in Joint Return Operations, including the use of Frontex support and compliance with common EU operational standards (e.g., joint removal guidelines, standardised readmission forms, and digital systems)?		Do national authorities actively participate in Joint Return Operations and request Frontex support when needed?
			Are joint return operations conducted consistently with EU standards in practice, including joint removal guidelines, monitoring compliance with fundamental rights, reporting outcomes, and employing centralized oversight mechanisms?

EU-level reporting & coordination	Is there a formal mechanism for reporting and coordinating with the Commission and EU institutions on progress, obstacles, and capacity gaps?	Does reporting and coordination with the Commission and EU institutions function effectively in practice to identify and address progress, obstacles, and capacity gaps?
Indicator 2:	Formal EU-Level Agreements & Support Instruments	Implementation of Formal EU Cooperation Frameworks and Funding Instruments
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Formal policy coherence & commitment	Does the return policy explicitly incorporate EU Readmission Agreements (EURA) and their implementing protocols?	To what extent is the EURA actively implemented by the returning and returned state?
	Is the given states a signatory to an EURA?	Is the EURA actively used in practice to facilitate returns, including through operational cooperation and readmission requests?
Conditionality & incentives	Is the existing EURA referring to incentives (e.g., trade preferences, visa facilitation)?	How effectively are incentives used to secure the country's cooperation in returns?
	Does the existing EURA include conditionality clauses linked to cooperation in return?	Is there any evidence that the conditionality clauses in the EURA are being applied and that they are affecting cooperation on returns?
Stakeholder participation	To what extent are relevant stakeholders involved in the negotiation and formulation of the EURA?	To what extent are relevant stakeholders involved in the implementation and monitoring of the EURA?
Support instruments	Does the return policy explicitly provide for the use of EU funding mechanisms (e.g., AMIF, previously ERF) to support return-related policies and operations?	To what extent does the state actively utilize EU funds to support return-related policies and operations?
Indicator 3:	Bilateral and Informal Arrangements	Functioning of Readmission Mechanisms
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
	Are there formal (legally binding) bilateral agreements?	To what extent are bilateral agreements or MoUs with third countries actively implemented, and are their provisions followed in practice?

Bilateral cooperation framework	Are there informal (flexible) arrangements or ad-hoc cooperation informal deals with third countries?	Are mechanisms for informal arrangements or ad-hoc cooperation with third countries actually used in practice?
Transparency	Do bilateral or informal return arrangements ensure transparent negotiation processes and stakeholder access to texts?	Are bilateral or informal return arrangements perceived and experienced in practice as transparent and accessible by relevant stakeholders?
Implementation mechanisms	Is there a structured mechanism to ensure the conclusion of implementation protocols and the regular functioning of Joint Readmission Committees (JRCs) or Working Groups to monitor compliance?	Are implementation protocols actually concluded in practice?
Operational coordination & facilitation of returns	Are there extra mechanisms and practices to facilitate cooperation with third countries on issuing or accepting EU travel documents for return?	Are there any reported cases where certain third countries are unwilling to cooperate in issuing or accepting EU travel documents for return?
	Is the role of Return Liaison Officers formally defined in the return framework to support identification, readmission procedures, and coordination with the Commission?	Do national authorities effectively use Return Liaison Officers or Frontex-supported experts in practice to support identification, documentation, and coordination during readmission procedures?
Indicator 4:	Alignment with Non-Migration Policies	Policy Coherence and Alignment
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Policy coordination	Is the return strategy formally integrated into development policy frameworks?	Do migration authorities coordinate in practice with foreign affairs, development, and labour/economic authorities when implementing return, reintegration, or alternative measures?
Diaspora engagement	Do the national migration policy documents incorporate diaspora engagement measures (e.g. incentives, skills transfer, investment) to support voluntary return or reintegration?	Are diaspora networks consulted or involved in planning return/reintegration programs?

Stage 3: Outcomes

This stage moves beyond formal compliance and implementation processes to examine both the direct policy effects of return governance and its broader consequences. It examines the actual effects of return policies by analysing the quantitative outcomes, qualitative outcomes including external/relational outcomes, reintegration trajectories, and broader individual or societal impacts, and any unintended or substitutive effects. Outcomes are operationalized across five main dimensions. A set of guiding evaluation questions is formulated to structure the analysis of each dimension through several indicators and/or measurement focus. Although there are indicators that point to measurable indicators (such as return volumes or efficiency ratios), they primarily serve as “measurement focuses” that organise multiple data sources, metrics, qualitative observations and contextual analysis around different outcome dimensions.

1st Dimension- Direct Policy Effects

Direct policy effects refer to the most immediate and observable outcomes of return governance, that are the level, composition, or direction of returns. The key direct effect of return governance is the total number of individuals who leave a host country. However, assessment cannot rely on return numbers alone. Beyond volume, direct effects also concern the composition of returnees. Finally, the direction of returns refers to the geographical flow of returnees, which is heavily shaped by return diplomacy and readmission agreements (e.g., EU-Georgia readmission agreement, see Jarosiewicz et al. 2025). Accordingly, as the first dimension addresses direct policy effects, it is operationalised through three key indicators:

Indicator/Measurement Focus 1: Return Figures (Volume & Efficiency)

Direct and observable policy outcomes of return governance include both the *volume* of returns and the *efficiency* with which return decisions are implemented. Key quantitative indicators track trends in return volumes and implementation rates, and assess efficiency by comparing the number of returns actually implemented with the number of return decisions issued. Returns are distinguished between voluntary and forced, while cancellations and delays, unverified exits, absconding rates, and re-entry patterns are further evaluated to capture structural constraints, compliance dynamics, and enforcement limitations.

Indicator/Measurement Focus 2: Change in Composition (Profile of Returnees)

This refers to the profiles of those who actually return, by status, gender, age, skill, nationality, vulnerability, and different return modalities. The focus is on *who* is returned, rather than how many. Beyond total return figures, changes in the profile of returnees (shifts in the demographic, legal, and vulnerability profiles) may reflect differences in implementation priorities, cooperation constraints, legal safeguards, or access conditions to voluntary return programs.

Indicator/Measurement Focus 3: Geographical Direction/ Destination Pattern

This measurement focuses on tracking where returnees actually go—whether they stay in their country of origin or move to a third country—and how these return flows change geographically over time in response to policies. This concerns the geographical direction or destination pattern of return flows. By pinpointing leading destination countries and regional groups, this indicator illuminates the spatial aspect of return outcomes and whether returns are becoming more concentrated, diversified, or if their direction is shifting. Beyond simple mapping, this analysis also considers how diplomatic relations, levels of cooperation, and formal readmission frameworks influence the actual direction of returns.

STAGE 3:		OUTCOMES
DIMENSION 1	DIRECT POLICY EFFECTS	
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS 1:	Return Figures (Volume & Efficiency)	
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Trend in return volume	How have total voluntary and enforced returns changed over time (year-on-year or within the assessment period)?	
Implementation rate of return decisions	What share of return decisions are actually implemented during the assessment period? (actual returns ÷ return decisions issued)	
Voluntary vs. enforced balance	What proportion of returns are voluntary vs. enforced?	
AVR-R	What share of voluntary returns are assisted voluntary returns (AVR-R)?	
Cancellations and delays	What share of return operations are cancelled or delayed, and what are the main reasons (e.g., legal, operational, third-country cooperation)?	
Policy-outcome alignment/gap	How do actual return outcomes compare to stated policy targets or benchmarks?	
Unverified exits	What proportion of individuals issued a return decision cannot be verified as having left the country?	
Absconding rate	What percentage of individuals subject to the return procedure abscond before the return process is completed?	
Re-entry	What proportion of returned individuals are detected re-entering irregularly within a defined period?	
INDICATOR /	Change in Composition (Profile of Returnees)	

MEASUREMENT FOCUS 2:	
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Gender & minors	What percentage of returnees are women, men, and minors?
Age distribution	How has the age distribution of returnees changed over time? ⁸
Nationality	Which countries account for the largest share of returnees (top five)?
	Is there a change in the share of top five nationalities subject to removal during the assessment period compared to the previous period?
Orders vs. actual returns	Do the nationalities with the highest return orders correspond to the nationalities with the highest actual returns?
Profiles by return types	How does the profile of returnees differ across voluntary, assisted voluntary, and enforced return modalities?
Vulnerable groups	Has the share of vulnerable groups among returnees changed over time?
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS 3:	
Thematic Focus	Geographical Direction/ Destination Pattern
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions
Top destination countries	What are the main destination countries to which returnees are actually sent? (top five countries)
Geographical pattern	Has the geographical distribution of return destinations changed over time or across assessment periods?
Regional clustering	Are returns geographically concentrated in specific regional clusters?
Diplomacy & cooperation effects	To what extent do cooperation levels with specific third countries influence the direction of returns?
Alignment with readmission agreements	Are return destinations aligned with countries that have formal readmission agreements?
Deviation from origin country	Are some return decisions being converted to returns to alternative third countries instead of the origin countries, and under what circumstances?

⁸ Possible coding approach might be categorical, not a score based, for example A – No significant change; B – Increase in younger returnees; C – Increase in working-age returnees; D – Increase in older returnees; E – Mixed or fluctuating pattern; F – Data not available.

2nd Dimension- External / Relational Outcomes

The actual implementation of returns is also largely influenced by external and relational factors beyond the unilateral control of the returning state. Return outcomes depend not only on the formal existence of cooperation frameworks but also on the quality and legitimacy of cooperation as perceived by third countries. The willingness and capacity of partner states to cooperate on return and readmission are affected by whether return cooperation is experienced as mutually beneficial, politically acceptable, and normatively legitimate. Additionally, the influence of power asymmetries and historical relationships on cooperation patterns and outcomes is important to understand for assessing compliance and operational effectiveness.

We grouped all these thematic focuses under a single indicator/measurement focus: **Return Cooperation with Third Countries**.

STAGE 3:		OUTCOMES
DIMENSION 2	EXTERNAL / RELATIONAL OUTCOMES	
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS:	Return Cooperation with Third Countries	
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Cooperation effectiveness	Do formal EU-level agreements contribute to higher rates of return or readmission?	
	What proportion of returns occur under EU readmission agreements, bilateral agreements, or informal arrangements?	
Normative & relational outcomes	Does return cooperation help strengthen mutual trust and promote long-term sustainability with partner countries?	
	Do the origin countries perceive a trade-off between sovereignty and cooperation on returns?	
	Is return cooperation perceived domestically in origin countries as fair and mutually agreed, or as externally imposed?	
Power relations	Have return partnerships led to the creation or expansion of bilateral labor migration schemes or legal mobility channels, legal regular pathways?	
	Are cooperation patterns among partner states affected by historical ties or dependence on development aid?	

3rd Dimension- Reintegration Outcomes

This dimension shifts the focus from the act of physical removal to the post-return experiences, treating reintegration capacity in the country of origin as a core benchmark for the sustainability and durability of return (see further GAPs WP8 reports). Reintegration is a multidimensional, context-dependent process that resists simple quantification and cannot be adequately captured through standardised indicators alone and reintegration policies should therefore be accompanied by monitoring and evaluation mechanisms that track short, medium, and long-term outcomes. We, nevertheless, propose a framework-oriented measurement focus that does not claim to fully capture reintegration outcomes, but systematizes core capacity-related elements in origin countries. This framework is operationalized through guiding evaluation questions on policy commitment, institutional and administrative capacity, service availability, and monitoring, brought together under a single indicator/measurement focus: **Reintegration Capacity in Origin Country**

STAGE 3:		OUTCOMES	
DIMENSION 3		REINTEGRATION OUTCOMES	
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS:		Reintegration Capacity in Origin Country	
Thematic Focus		Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Policy commitment	Do national or local institutions demonstrate explicit interest or political commitment to reintegration of returnees (e.g., via strategies, policies, or official action plans)?		
Administrative capacity	Does the origin country have administrative capacity to support reintegration (e.g., case management systems, coordination of reintegration services)?		
Institutional capacity	Is there a designated national authority or office for return and reintegration, and does it have sustainable funding for reintegration programmes?		
Reintegration services	Are essential reintegration services available and accessible (e.g., employment support, psychosocial services, housing, vocational training, legal aid)?		
	Do reintegration services address specific needs of vulnerable returnees (e.g., women, youth, children, people with disabilities)?		
Utilization	What proportion of returnees were able to access available reintegration services?		
Economic reintegration/ labour market capacity	How adequate is labour market in the origin country in terms of job availability, sectoral demand, and employability pathways for returnees?		
Monitoring	Are monitoring systems in place to track reintegration outcomes for returnees?		

4th Dimension - Individual and Social Outcomes

The return of migrants to their countries of origin, whether voluntary or forced, creates a complex range of individual, local, and social impacts. To evaluate outcomes in this area, it is essential to go beyond merely completing return procedures and investigate whether returns foster sustainable reintegration, social inclusion, and long-term stability, or whether they instead perpetuate vulnerability and marginalisation.⁹ To analyse these effects, this area is structured around two complementary measurement focuses that address both individual well-being and community-level social dynamics: **(1) Migrants’ Well-Being / Sustainable Reintegration and (2) Community & Social Impact.**

STAGE 3:		OUTCOMES
DIMENSION 4		INDIVIDUAL AND SOCIAL OUTCOMES
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS 1:		Migrants’ Well-Being / Sustainable Reintegration
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Livelihoods	Do returnees secure stable and sustainable livelihoods within 12 months of return?	
Living conditions & well-being	Are returnees’ living conditions, safety, and overall well-being improving after return?	
Rights protection	Are returnees’ human and legal rights (protection needs) respected during and after return?	
Re-migration intention / behaviour	Do returnees intend to re-migrate to the returning country or elsewhere?	
	What proportion of returnees re-migrate within the assessment period (% of total returns)?	
Exposure to chain deportation	Are returnees exposed to chain deportations in transit countries?	
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS 2:		Community & Social Impact
Thematic Focus	Guiding Evaluation Questions	
Community acceptance / stigma	Do local communities accept returnees, or do returnees face stigma, discrimination, or social exclusion?	
Social tension	Are there incidents of social tension, disputes, or conflict related to the arrival of returnees?	

⁹ See further GAPs D5.2. <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/research-digest-key-insights-on-nigeria-eu-migration-cooperation?rq=Nigeria>.

Media portrayal	How are returnees portrayed in local and national media (positive, neutral, or negative framing e.g., as burden, threat etc.)?
Public messaging	Does public messaging influence local community perceptions of returnees?
Local development	To what extent does the reintegration of returnees contribute to local development, including economic, social, or cultural benefits?

5th Dimension- Substitutive Effects

Policy restrictions and other measures can generate unintended effects on return migration flows, including the diversion of routes to other countries or into more irregular routes after return policies are enforced. To evaluate policy effectiveness, it is therefore necessary to account for such substitutive dynamics, which may obscure or distort the interpretation of observed return outcomes. By examining shifts in migration routes, burden shifting across migration control mechanisms, and situations that produce a legal limbo for non-removable returnees, this dimension captures policy externalities (Czaika & Haas 2013) in which restrictive measures produce results contrary to their stated objectives.

STAGE 3:		OUTCOMES
DIMENSION 5		SUBSTITUTIVE EFFECTS
INDICATOR / MEASUREMENT FOCUS:		Substitution and Unintended Effects
Thematic Focus		Guiding Evaluation Questions
Shift in routes		Do monitoring data, field reports, or expert assessments show unintended shifts toward riskier or irregular migration routes following return policy enforcement?
Burden shifting		Do return policies displace migration pressures to alternative mechanisms (e.g., overstaying visas, irregular residence) or reduce pressure on asylum and border systems?
Non-removable returnees		Do deterrence measures (e.g., linking welfare benefits to legal status, criminalizing irregular stay) generate or expand a group of ‘non-removable returnees’ who cannot be returned nor regularized?
		What is the size of the non-removable returnee population (persons with a return decision who cannot be returned due to lack of identification, documentation, or refusal by the origin country)?

5. Scoring Logic, Scaling and Weighting Framework

Foundational Principles

Before defining the scoring logic, three consecutive decisions should generally be made in the development of an index: conceptualisation, measurement, and aggregation (Munck et al. 2002; OECD, 2008; Bjerre et al. 2017; Helbling et al. 2017). The conceptualisation stage was described in detail above. As Bjerre et al. (2015) establish, choices made at the conceptualisation stage cascade into all subsequent methodological decisions. Similarly, Munck and Verkuilen (2002) caution that scoring aggregation rules must reflect the underlying theoretical relationship between components: additive aggregation implies substitutability, while multiplicative aggregation implies necessity. This implies that the choice of aggregation levels is determined by the conceptual framework – what gets combined and with what.

Before proceeding to quantify the suggested framework, the researcher or policymaker should address several key questions:

1. **Weighting justification.** As Helbling et al. (2017) observe, the relative importance of index components cannot be determined objectively. Whether weights are equal, theory-derived, or expert-assigned, they need to be explicitly justified. Additionally, where possible, the weights should undergo sensitivity analysis to assess whether results vary significantly under different weighting schemes (OECD, 2008).
2. **Theoretical stance on necessity vs. substitutability.** This is not a technical question but a substantive one. Does the researcher/policymaker believe, for example, that a country with formal bilateral agreements but no independent monitoring should score higher than one with moderate performance across all dimensions? The answer determines aggregation logic.
3. **Whether to apply floor penalties or thresholds.** Regardless of the aggregation method, the researcher should consider whether certain indicators - especially procedural safeguards and rights guarantees - should have a minimum threshold below which the overall score is capped. This emphasises the non-negotiable nature of certain legal or normative obligations and is independent of whether addition or multiplication is used.
4. **Level of aggregation.** The researcher/policymaker must decide whether to produce a single composite score, dimension-level scores, or both (Helbling et. al 2017). Disaggregated scores preserve more information and are more useful diagnostically – identifying where gaps lie – while a composite score is more useful for cross-country comparison.

General Scaling Logic

For Stage 1 and 2 described above, each indicator across all three dimensions might be scored on a 0–3 ordinal scale, reflecting three observable levels:

Score	Stage 1.Policy-on-Paper	Stage 2.Implementation
0	No relevant legal provision, definition, or formal commitment exists	No evidence of operational practice, enforcement, or application of the relevant provision
1	A provision exists but is vague, inconsistent across legal instruments, or incomplete in scope	Practice occurs sporadically or inconsistently; significant variation across cases, regions, or actors
2	A clear provision exists but contains notable gaps, ambiguities, or lacks accompanying procedural detail	Practice is generally present but with documented gaps, exceptions, or limited accountability for non-compliance
3	A comprehensive, consistent, and clear legal framework is in place across all relevant instruments	Practice is consistent, verifiable through evidence, and subject to accountability mechanisms

This approach is consistent with the IMPIC methodology (Helbling et al., 2017), which stresses that items must vary across countries and be comparable. Ordinal scaling might be favoured over binary coding here because, in many cases, return migration governance exists on a continuum rather than as a simple presence or absence condition. It is important to note that the rating scale could vary, such as from 0 to 7, if the context requires it. However, the meaning of each rating must remain clear. More options and a discussion on the nuances of setting minimums and maximums in ordinal variables, including the potential for half-points, are thoroughly explained in Heible et al. (2017).

For Stage 3 (Outcomes), a mix of quantitative and ordinary scales might be used due to the nature of the dimensions given.

General Indicator Weighing

Within each dimension and stage, several indicators are employed to assess the relevant criteria. Indicators may involve different numbers of guiding evaluation questions or sub-items. To ensure comparability across indicators despite these differences, each indicator should first be standardised to a common internal scale before aggregating at the dimension level. Often, this is already achieved when a shared ordinal scoring scale—such as the 0-3 framework described above—is utilised.

In such cases, the indicator score should be obtained by averaging all sub-question scores and rounding to the nearest whole number. The rounding procedure itself should be made transparent, for instance, by specifying the threshold at which decimal values are rounded upward or downward. Where certain sub-questions are clearly more central to the indicator’s conceptual focus, the researcher or policymaker may assign higher internal weights to those items before

averaging. As with the framework, the key in this process is transparency in documenting these choices. Alternatively, a multiplicative aggregation may be employed when one or more sub-questions are necessary conditions rather than optional or interchangeable elements. In such cases, scoring zero on a critical sub-question would significantly limit or even nullify the overall indicator score. A hybrid method is also available, where essential sub-questions are multiplied together, and the resulting score is then averaged with the other sub-questions.

It should be noted that indicator estimation involves more steps and nuances than those explained here that is also relevant to GAPs indicator development exercise. For example, the OECD Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators (2008) offers a detailed guidance on how to proceed with careful data selection, how to deal with missing data, or how to standardise and normalise values when they are not on the same scale (or distribution). It also provides a more detailed explanation of the procedures for conducting a sensitivity analysis. In other words, given that “subjective choices are the bones of the composite indicator,” the process goes beyond merely verifying whether the assigned weights are appropriate. It enables practitioners to “perform X-rays” of the model by systematically examining the relationship between the “information flowing in and out of the model” (OECD, 2008, p. 117). Another crucial aspect to consider is the validity of the data sources, as well as the specific biases and measurement errors each may introduce. One way to address this is to rely on several sources that do not depend on one another. If the analysis relies too heavily on subjective assessments or draws solely on official data whose credibility is doubtful, the results may be weakened. In such situations, facilitating replication of the findings and maintaining transparency about the data used are necessary steps.¹⁰

Considerations for Weighting at Stages 1 and 2

Dimension 1: Legal Framework and Implementation Consistency

This dimension assesses whether formal legal commitments are translated into practice. It contains three indicators, each capturing a distinct layer of the policy-to-practice chain.

- I1: Presence and Clarity of Legal Framework
- I2: Procedural Safeguards and Rights Guarantees
- I3: Independent Monitoring and Reporting

If the researcher/policymakers decide that procedural safeguards are a necessary condition, multiplicative aggregation within this dimension is appropriate, and a score of zero on I2 would collapse the dimension score. This reflects the rights-based floor approach. If the researcher/policymakers treat components as substitutable, additive aggregation applies. In either case, the researcher should consider whether a minimum threshold on I2, or within I2 a multiplicative approach is needed, beyond the aggregation method chosen for the overall dimension. Same considerations for I1 and I3.

For the overall dimension, an additive measure could be used with a weight defined by the researcher/policymaker as a percentage. Additionally, researchers/policymakers should decide

¹⁰ A deeper discussion on these topics can be found in Bjerre et al. (2015) as well as in Munck et. al (2002).

whether to report a policy-on-paper sub-score (encompassing I1–I3) and a separate implementation sub-score (encompassing also I1–I3), which would then be aggregated (by weighting or summation) or computed as a single score from the start. If combining, a possibility could be to give the implementation score a larger weight than the paper score.

Dimension 2: Institutional and Administrative Design

This dimension captures the operational backbone of return governance: capacity, coordination, and procedural efficiency. It consists of the next indicators:

- I1: Clarity of Roles, Mandates and Institutional Configuration
- I2: Domestic Coordination Mechanisms
- I3: Financial and Resource Capacity
- I4: Stakeholder Involvement
- I5: Digital Infrastructure and Data Management

A suggestion here would need to specify whether the weight of roles, mandates, and resource capacity should be considered equally, given that institutional clarity without resources or resources without clear mandates could both lead to governance failure. Additionally, it would be necessary to clarify whether stakeholder involvement and digital infrastructure are enabling or constitutive features. If all indicators here are theoretically interchangeable, then they could simply be combined. The weight would depend, as previously mentioned, on whether some are considered more or less important. As in dimension 1, the researcher/policymaker should decide whether to proceed using two sub.scores or with just a single one from the outset.

Dimension 3: International Cooperation

Given that physical return is inherently an international act requiring third-country consent, this dimension has a distinct character: without minimum cooperation, return governance cannot produce outcomes regardless of domestic quality. The indicators are the next:

- I1: Intra-EU Policy Coherence between National and EU Frameworks
- I2: Formal EU-Level Agreements and Support Instruments
- I3: Bilateral and Informal Arrangements
- I4: Alignment with Non-Migration Policies

In this case, the researcher/policymaker should decide if formal and informal bilateral arrangements receive equal highest weights, reflecting that operational return practice depends on both – formal agreements set the architecture while informal arrangements often drive day-to-day execution. The others could be determined using the same approach. As before, whether to use aggregation or multiplication depends on the context the researcher or policymaker faces. Finally, the researcher or policymaker should once again decide whether to proceed with sub-scores and combine them or to start with just one from the beginning.

Aggregation for Stages 1 and 2

Before cross-dimensional aggregation is applied, the researcher must first decide how the policy-on-paper and implementation strands established at indicator level are carried forward. Three

pathways are available. **The first** combines policy-on-paper and implementation sub-scores into a single indicator score prior to dimension aggregation, using either a weighted or unweighted method as determined at the indicator level. This results in one dimension score and ultimately a single composite index. **The second** keeps policy-on-paper and implementation sub-scores separate throughout dimension aggregation, resulting in two parallel dimension scores — one for policy-on-paper and one for implementation — which are only compared rather than combined in each dimension. These two approaches have been already explained in the above paragraphs. **The third approach**, however, would be to never combine the two strands at any level, treating policy-on-paper and implementation as two separate indices from indicator level to final output. In other words, the final output of stages one and two would be two overall indicators, each reflecting one side.

Once this pathway decision is made, and regardless of whether researchers or policymakers opt for one or two overall indicators for this stage, it must be decided whether the dimensions are substitutable or necessary in relation to one another:

- An additive approach produces a composite score where strong institutional design can partially offset weaker international cooperation. In other words, the impact of weak score dimensions in the overall can be offset by strong scores in the others.
- A multiplicative approach treats all dimensions as jointly necessary, meaning weakness in anyone cannot be compensated elsewhere.
- A hybrid approach — for example multiplying dimensions 1 and 3 while adding dimension 2 — reflects a more nuanced theoretical position where some dimensions are necessary to one another while others remain enabling.

Whatever approach is chosen, the importance assigned to each component cannot be determined objectively in advance. It is therefore essential to explain the reasoning behind the chosen weights and to test how results change under different weighting options.

Considerations for Weighting at Stage 3

Outcome dimensions require a different measurement logic from policy dimensions. Rather than ordinal scoring of governance quality, outcome indicators rely on quantitative administrative and statistical data where available and supplemented by qualitative assessments where such data are lacking. Scores should still be normalised to a common scale (0–100 for example) to allow aggregation, but the researcher/policymaker must state clearly the reference point used, whether this is a country's prior performance, regional averages, or a theoretical/normative ideal.

Dimension 1: Direct Policy Effects

This dimension captures the most proximate measurable consequences of return policy, through the following indicators explained above:

- I1. Return Figures (Volume and Efficiency)
- I2. Change in Composition (Profile of Returnees)
- I3. Geographical Direction/Destination Pattern

The researcher/policymaker must decide whether volume alone is a meaningful indicator, and whether it should be contextualised against the total numbers subject to return orders – raw return numbers without a denominator can be deeply misleading. Composition and directional changes are analytically important for detecting displacement or substitution effects and should not be collapsed into volume measures. Additive aggregation within this dimension could be appropriate, as the three measurements are conceptually distinct but not hierarchically different.

Dimension 2: External and Relational Outcomes

This dimension captures effects on relationships with third countries and within EU cooperation frameworks – the relational consequences of how return policy is operationalised, beyond whether individual returns occur. The indicators here are:

- I1. Cooperation Effectiveness
- I2. Normative and Relational Outcomes
- I3. Power Relations

Indicators here are harder to operationalise quantitatively and may rely substantially on qualitative or expert-coded assessments. The researcher/policymaker must decide what counts as a measurable relational outcome regarding changes in bilateral agreement status, third-country cooperation ratings, or shifts in EU burden-sharing arrangements. Given the qualitative nature of many indicators, the researcher/policymaker should consider whether simple additive scoring is appropriate or whether a more holistic expert-rating approach better captures relational complexity.

A word of caution on the use of experts is that they should all be able to rate the items using the same criteria – possibly through training or guidance - even if they hold different types of knowledge and experience. This is to avoid the scores not being comparable in the future (Helbling et al. 2017).

Dimension 3: Reintegration Outcomes

A sustainable return requires that returnees reintegrate into their countries of origin – a condition that extends beyond mere statistics of return. This aspect, therefore, broadens the assessment beyond the moment of physical removal.

- I1. Policy Commitment
- I2. Administrative Capacity
- I3. Institutional Capacity
- I4. Reintegration Services
- I5. Utilisation
- I6. Economic Reintegration/Labour Market Capacity
- I7. Monitoring

Reintegration outcomes are among the most difficult to measure systematically, given data limitations in countries of origin. The researcher/policymaker must decide on the time horizon

for measurement — reintegration is a process, not an event — and on the level of analysis, whether individual, community, or country. Where data are unavailable, proxy indicators such as re-migration rates or access to reintegration support programmes may be used, but their limitations should be acknowledged.

Dimension 4: Individual and Social Outcomes

This dimension captures the human consequences of return at the individual and community level, including wellbeing, rights observance during and after return, and social reintegration, by using the following indicators.

- I1. Livelihoods
- I2. Living Conditions & Well-Being
- I3. Rights Protection
- I4. Re-migration Intention/Behaviour
- I5. Exposure to Chain Deportation
- I6. Community Acceptance/Stigma
- I7. Social Tension
- I8. Media Portrayal
- I9. Public Messaging
- I10. Local Development

Individual and social outcomes are the furthest from conventional policy metrics and the most dependent on qualitative, survey-based, or case study evidence as well as expert evaluations. The researcher must decide how much weight this dimension carries relative to more quantifiable dimensions. This choice is ultimately normative and subjective rather than technical. The researcher/policymaker should be explicit about this rather than treating it as a neutral technical decision.

Dimension 5: Substitutive Effects

This dimension addresses the possibility that return policy produces unintended consequences — most notably that enforcement of a single return pathway displaces rather than reduces irregular stay, or that a focus on voluntary return reduces forced return without affecting overall irregular migration levels, by the following indicators.

- I1. Shift in Routes
- I2. Burden Shifting
- I3. Non-Removable Returnees

Substitutive effects are inherently difficult to measure, as they require constructing a counterfactual (for more on this topic consult Cunningham, 2021). The researcher/policymaker must decide whether this dimension is scored positively (i.e., the absence of substitution as a governance achievement) or used as a corrective modifier applied to some dimension 1 scores—reducing apparent policy effectiveness when substitution effects are detected. At minimum, and largely the most feasible, the researcher/policymaker should include this dimension as a transparency mechanism: even if it cannot be fully scored, a binary score that flags the presence

or absence of evidence for substitutive effects prevents the index from overstating direct policy success.

Aggregation for Stage Three

The five outcome dimensions span very different types of evidence — quantitative administrative data, relational assessments, longitudinal reintegration data, individual-level wellbeing, and counterfactual substitution effects. Additive aggregation across these dimensions assumes they are commensurable, which is a strong assumption the researcher/policymaker must justify. An alternative approach is to present dimension scores separately rather than collapsing them into a single outcome score, reserving aggregation for within-dimension calculations – if appropriate.

Overall Index Aggregation

The researcher must finally decide how Stages 1–2 and Stage 3 relate to one another in the overall index. Three positions are possible here:

A purely additive overall score treats policy-on-paper, implementation quality, and outcomes as substitutable, implying that strong governance processes can partially compensate for weak outcomes. This alternative can also be used where outcome data are unreliable.

A multiplicative relationship treats outcomes as the ultimate validation of implementation quality and policy design, meaning that strong policy and institutional design that produces no measurable outcomes scores poorly overall.

Three or two-component reported index, by presenting policy-on-paper, implementation and outcome scores separately (or whether the first two were combined in Stage 1 as explained above) without collapsing them into one single index score, preserves the most analytical information and avoids forcing a theoretical position on the design-implementation-outcome relationship that the evidence may not support for the specific context.

6. Concluding Remarks

This Indicator Proposal has set out a structured, conceptually, analytically and empirically grounded framework for assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of return governance across three interlinked stages: policies-on-paper, implementation, and outcomes. By combining instrumental dimensions (legal clarity, institutional design, coordination, financial and human resources, data infrastructures) with normative ones (rights safeguards, protection standards, reintegration sustainability), it offers a way to move beyond narrow return rate metrics and to disentangle how formal commitments, practices, and observed effects relate to one another in different contexts. The proposed dimensions and indicators, along with their guiding questions and scalable scoring options, are designed as an analytical toolkit rather than a rigid final index, allowing for context-sensitive diagnosis of strengths, gaps, and trade-offs in return governance.

The framework can be utilised in various ways and expanded over time. Researchers and policymakers can apply it to single-country or comparative case studies, develop stage- or dimension-specific indices, or choose particular indicators based on needs such as monitoring, evaluation, and reform discussions. Pilot applications, as a whole and selected parts, could test feasibility, refine the guiding questions, and calibrate scoring and weighting choices, while sensitivity analyses would help assess how robust results are to different aggregation strategies. Over the longer term, the proposal could be expanded through better outcome data (especially on reintegration and individual/social impacts), integration of additional contextual layers (e.g., structural drivers and non-migration policies), and closer involvement of stakeholders and returnees in validating both indicators and ratings. In this sense, the framework should be seen as a starting point for cumulative methodological guideline (toolbox) on return governance effectiveness, open to adaptation, revision, and co-production in future research and policy initiatives.

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About the Authors

Fatma Yılmaz-Elmas, research associate at Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies

Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek, GAPS coordinator and senior research fellow at Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies

Rodrigo Bolaños Suárez, research fellow at Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies

Soner Barthoma, researcher at Uppsala University

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